

Creating end-of-service-life datasets for construction materials and products

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Abstract

The UK construction industry is the largest consumer of natural resources estimated at 400 million tonnes and producing about 100 million tonnes of waste yearly. The volume of waste produced during construction activities and demolition exercise in the United Kingdom accounted for 62% of total waste in 2018. This research identifies the gap in data inconsistencies, reporting, collection, harmonization, accessibility, and storage.

Digitization of life cycle information about materials and products in construction brings solutions for ease of accessibility, interoperability, and upcycling. The purpose of the project is to identify sets of data required and develop datasets for the end-of-service-life of materials and products in construction.

The process of creating the dataset will involve reviewing the existing procedure on how data is collected and working with material passports for product life cycle management.

The waste-related dataset created about the materials and products in construction during the pre-demolition audit will be useful in decision making on waste management and recovery. This will contribute to the digitization process of pre-demolition audits which will: help in maximum recovery of materials and products from buildings set for demolition, make traceability easier, reduce construction and demolition waste, and lower the amounts of natural resources consumed by the construction industry.

Keywords

Construction and demolition waste, pre-demolition audit, resource efficiency, circular economy, and material passport.

Format

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